

***In silico* approach towards the Anti-Obesity effects of Flaxseed Components Alpha
Linolenic Acid and Secoisolariciresinol Diglucoside by the inhibition of SOCS3 – The
inhibitor of Leptin Signalling Pathway**

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Abstract:

One of the key features of obesity is leptin resistance, which refers to reduced sensitivity to the hormone leptin. Chronic exposure to leptin is believed to cause desensitization of the leptin receptor and impair leptin signalling, particularly through the SOCS3 (Suppressor of Cytokine Signalling 3) pathway. Studies in mice have linked SOCS3 to the development of leptin resistance and obesity, as the deletion or knockdown of SOCS3 improves leptin sensitivity and protects against diet-induced obesity. While diet and exercise are the primary treatments for obesity, medications can be used as adjuncts to assist some individuals in losing weight. However, these drugs often come with numerous adverse effects and primarily target absorption and hormone levels, without addressing the underlying signalling issue. This study focuses on the potential role of flaxseed compounds as ligands in obesity prevention and management. Flaxseed components, particularly Secoisolariciresinol diglucoside and α -Linolenic acid, have been investigated for their anti-obesity activity using in silico methods. Molecular docking studies using Glide were performed to assess their interactions with the target protein SOCS3. Furthermore, the stability of the binding was evaluated through Molecular Dynamics Simulation studies using Desmond. These investigations indicate that both Secoisolariciresinol diglucoside and α -Linolenic acid, found in flaxseed components, exhibit promising potential as nutraceuticals for obesity prevention.

Keywords: Obesity, Secoisolariciresinol diglucoside, α -Linolenic acid, Flaxseed, Nutraceutical, SOCS3.

Introduction:

Obesity is a chronic disease caused by an imbalance in energy intake and expenditure, resulting in the accumulation of excess body fat (1). It is a complicated condition with multiple causes, including genetic, environmental, and behavioural factors, and is linked to serious health risks such as cardiovascular disease, type 2 diabetes, and certain types of cancer (2). Obesity has emerged as a major global public health concern, 39% of adults were reported to be overweight and 18% of children between the ages 5-19 were reported to be either overweight or obese in 2016 (3).

Obesity has a strong genetic component, with estimates ranging from 40% to 70% heritability (4). Researchers have identified several genes associated with an increased risk of obesity, including those involved in appetite regulation, metabolism, and energy expenditure (5). For instance, mutations in the melanocortin-4 receptor gene (MC4R) have been linked to severe early-onset obesity in both humans and animals (6). However, genetic factors alone cannot fully account for the current obesity epidemic, as obesity prevalence has risen dramatically in recent decades, suggesting the importance of environmental and behavioural factors (7). Obesity is associated with a variety of health problems, such as cardiovascular disease, type 2 diabetes, certain cancers, and musculoskeletal disorders (8). The increased risk of these diseases in obesity is mediated by multiple physiological processes, including insulin resistance, chronic inflammation, and dyslipidemia (9).

Leptin is a hormone produced by adipose tissue that regulates energy balance and body weight. It signals the brain to reduce food intake and increase energy expenditure, while also playing a role in glucose metabolism, reproductive function, and immune function (10). In obesity, there is a decrease in sensitivity to Obesity is characterised by leptin resistance, or a decreased sensitivity to leptin known as leptin resistance, caused by chronic exposure to leptin, desensitizing the leptin receptor and impairing its signalling (11). Leptin resistance can lead to increased food intake and decreased energy expenditure, which may contribute to the development of obesity. Factors such as inflammation, oxidative stress, and changes in the gut microbiome contribute to leptin resistance (12). Inflammation and oxidative stress inhibit leptin receptor function, while changes in the gut microbiome impair leptin signalling (13,14). The JAK2-STAT3 pathway is involved in leptin signalling, and excessive or chronic stimulation of this pathway can lead to the development of leptin resistance (15).

SOCS3 (Suppressor of Cytokine Signalling 3) is a protein that negatively regulates leptin signalling and helps maintain metabolic homeostasis. It inhibits leptin signalling by binding to and inhibiting the activity of JAK2, the signalling protein. This prevents the activation of downstream transcription factor STAT3, which is

necessary for the expression of genes involved in food intake and energy expenditure regulation. SOCS3 plays a role in limiting the signalling response to leptin, preventing the development of leptin resistance by inhibiting JAK2 (16). SOCS3 has been linked to the development of leptin resistance and obesity in mice. SOCS3 deletion or knockdown in the hypothalamus, for example, improves leptin sensitivity and protects against diet-induced obesity (17). Overexpression of SOCS3 in the hypothalamus, on the other hand, causes leptin resistance and obesity (18,19). These findings highlight the significance of SOCS3 in regulating leptin signalling and the development of metabolic disorders.

Although diet and exercise are the primary treatments for obesity, medications can be used as a supplement to aid in weight loss. Some of the drugs used to treat obesity include orlistat, liraglutide, phentermine, and naltrexone/bupropion (20). However, these medications often come with various side effects such as blood pressure fluctuations and flatulence (21). These drugs only act on the level of absorption and at the level of hormone itself but do not address the root issue of the signalling. The potential health benefits of flaxseeds in relation to obesity have received particular attention. Flaxseeds are small brown or golden seeds high in fibre, omega-3 fatty acids, lignans, and other bioactive compounds. They have been used for thousands of years for medicinal purposes and have been shown to have a variety of health benefits, including improved digestive health, reduced inflammation, and lower cholesterol levels. Flaxseeds have also been investigated for their potential role in obesity prevention and management (22). Keeping this in view, we have taken the flaxseed compounds as the ligands of study. It is important to note that these medications primarily act on absorption or hormone levels and do not address the underlying signalling issue. Taking this into consideration, our study focusses on the investigation of flaxseed compounds as potential ligands.

The flax seed compounds ALA, also known as α -linolenic acid and Secoisolariciresinol diglucoside (SDG) were reported to have health benefits. ALA is a naturally occurring antioxidant found in foods such as spinach, broccoli, and potatoes. Some studies suggest that ALA may have weight loss and obesity benefits by improving insulin sensitivity. However, more research is needed to fully understand its effects, determine optimal dosages, and treatment duration (23). SDG is a compound found in flaxseeds and other plant-based foods. It has been studied for its potential role in weight management. There is evidence suggesting that SDG may aid in weight management for obese individuals. For instance, one study found that SDG supplementation led to reductions in body weight, BMI, and waist circumference in overweight and obese postmenopausal women. However, further research is necessary to validate these findings and establish optimal dosages and treatment durations for SDG supplementation (24). Hence this study aims to study the anti-obesity activity of flaxseed components especially

Secoisolariciresinol diglucoside (SDG) and Alpha Linolenic acid (ALA) through *in silico* methods by assessing the binding capability of the selected compounds with the target protein SOCS3.

Methodology:

Molecular docking studies.

The Protein Data Bank (PDB) was used to obtain the X-ray crystal structure of the target protein SOCS3 (PDB ID: 2HMH) (25). The ligand molecules SDG (CID: 9917980), ALA (CID: 5280934) and the control ligand Zoledronic Acid (CID: 68740) were retrieved from Pubchem. Maestro was used to visualize the downloaded structures (Schrödinger LLC, 2022-2). The Protein Preparation Wizard of Schrödinger suite was used to prepare the protein for molecular docking. Similarly, the ligand molecules were prepared using LigPrep. The glide grid file was created using the receptor grid generation panel, where the co-crystallized ligand situated at the protein's active site was selected to uncover the corresponding x, y, and z coordinates (-31.02, 21.89, and 30.09) automatically. The molecular docking was done with Glide software (26). The 2D plot of the interactions were plotted with the help of LigPlot+ v.2.2.8. software.

Molecular Dynamics Simulation.

All simulations were run with the OPLS-AA force field using the academic version of the MD simulation software, Desmond 6.9 (27). Desmond uses a specific neutral territory technique dubbed the midpoint approach to effectively take advantage of a high level of parallelism in the computation. The initial system for the MD simulation was set using the system builder panel. The complexes were built in the orthorhombic box and solvated with SPC water models (28). The systems were equilibrated using the NPT ensemble, based on the default desmond options. The systems were then subjected to a 150ns simulation production run with a relaxation time of 2ps. During the simulation, 1 atm pressure and 26.85°C temperature of the system were set using a Martyna-Klein barostat (29) and Nose-Hoover chain thermostat(30)

Fig 1: Workflow of the study

Results and Discussion:

To evaluate the potential effects of flaxseed compounds in managing obesity and diabetes, molecular docking and molecular dynamics simulations were conducted with the target protein SOCS3.

Molecular Docking Studies.

The molecular docking studies of SOCS3 with the flaxseed components especially Alpha-linolenic acid (ALA) and Secoisolariciresinol diglucoside (SDG) was done and Zoledronic acid, an inhibitor of SOS3 was taken as control. The study revealed that the compounds SDG and ALA shows high binding affinity with the target with a least docking score of -9.00 and -8.32 Kcal/mol respectively than that of the control ligand Zoledronic acid which has a binding energy of -6.03 Kcal/mol. The active site residues include Leu93, Leu104, Gln105, Ser106, Asp107, Arg109, Ser110, Gln112, Val114, Pro115, Tyr127, Arg140, Tyr142, Tyr143, Tyr145, Leu153. The residue Arg140 has been identified as playing a significant role in establishing hydrogen bonds with the oxygen atoms of compound ALA. Additionally, SDG (specific compound) formed five hydrogen bonds with the target, involving the residues Asp107, Leu104, Tyr143, Tyr145, and Tyr127. It is worth noting that the tyrosine residues contribute significantly to both the formation of hydrogen bonds and hydrophobic interactions with SDG. The residues interacting with the ligands forming hydrogen bonds and other interactions for each complex are shown in Table 1. The 2D plot of these interactions are shown in Fig 2, 3 and 4. Hence, from these results it can be inferred that the compounds ALA and SDG may have the potential for the inhibition of SOCS3 protein and thereby may have anti-obesity properties.

Table 1. Docking Results of SOCS3 with control and flaxseed components.

S.No.	Complex	Docking Score (Kcal/mol)	Interacting Residues (H Bonds)	Interacting Residues (Others)
1	2hnh – Zoledronic Acid (Control)	-6.03	Tyr107, Ser110, Tyr143, Lys150.	Ser106, Tyr127, Tyr142.
2	2hnh – Alpha-linolenic acid	-8.32	Arg140 (2)	Ser106, Asp107, Arg109, Ser110,

					Gln112, Pro115, Tyr127, Tyr142, Tyr143, Tyr145.
3	2hmh Secoisolariciresinol diglucoside	-	-9.00	Leu104, Asp107, Tyr127, Tyr143, Tyr145.	Leu93, Gln105, Ser110, Gln112, Val114, Tyr142, Ile144, Leu153.

Fig 2: 2D Interaction plot of SOCS3– Zoledronic acid (Control) complex. The ligand is shown in blue edges. Green dotted lines show the hydrogen bonds and the residues forming hydrophobic interactions are represented in red arcs.

Fig 3: 2D Interaction plot of 2nmh – Alpha-linolenic acid complex. The ligand is shown in blue edges. Green dotted lines show the hydrogen bonds and the residues forming hydrophobic interactions are represented in red arcs.

Fig 4: 2D Interaction plot of SOCS3 – Secoisolariciresinol diglucoside complex. The ligand is shown in blue edges. Green dotted lines show the hydrogen bonds and the residues forming hydrophobic interactions are represented in red arcs.

Molecular Dynamics Simulation

To evaluate the stability of the top docked complex, we performed molecular dynamics (MD) simulations on SOC3-SGD complex. Additionally, MD simulations of SOC3-Zoledronic acid complex was performed for comparison purposes. The simulations were conducted for a duration of 150 nanoseconds to capture potential conformational changes and system equilibration, ensuring a thorough assessment of the stability and dynamics of the complexes. The Root Mean Square Deviation (RMSD) of the targets in conjunction with the ligand molecules was monitored throughout the simulations. The RMSD indicates the extent of deviation of the atoms within the complexes from their initial reference structure. A high RMSD value suggests significant instability in the complex. The RMSD of the SGD bound complex exhibited a low value initially, and a slight increase was observed after 30 ns of the simulation. However, this increase in RMSD was subsequently found to be stabilized.

Comparatively both the control and SGD showed similar deviations. The Root Mean Square Fluctuation (RMSF) was utilized to assess the flexibility of the residues in the target proteins within the chosen complexes. Fluctuations were observed in 100 to 115 residues, which was also observed in the control, which might be due to the flexible nature of the residues.

Fig 5: RMSD of the complexes

Fig 6: RMSF of the protein upon binding of A) Secoisolariciresinol diglucoside and B) Zoledronic acid

Fig 7: Interaction histogram of the complexes of A) SOCS3 – Secoisolariciresinol diglucoside and B) SOCS3 – Zoledronic acid

The hydrogen bonds, hydrophobic interaction and salt bridges were calculated and the hydrogen bonds were assessed to validate the stable interactions from the docking results throughout the simulation time. The SOCS3-SDG complex exhibited a higher number of hydrogen bonds compared to the control complex, indicating greater stability of the complex.

SOCS3 is composed of an N-terminal region, a central SH2 domain, and a C-terminal SOCS3 box. The SH2 domain plays a crucial role in inhibiting signaling proteins either directly or competitively. Leptin, a hormone produced by fat cells, plays a crucial role in regulating hormonal and metabolic responses to changes in nutritional status by binding to and activating the long form of the leptin receptor (LRb) found in the hypothalamus. When a ligand binds to LRb, it triggers the activation and tyrosine phosphorylation of Jak2, which leads to the subsequent tyrosine phosphorylation of Tyr985 and Tyr1138 on LRb. The administration of leptin prompts the activation of STAT3-mediated transcription, resulting in the induction of SOCS3, which in turn, inhibits LRb signaling. In cell models of leptin resistance and certain obese animals, the levels of cellular SOCS3 are elevated, suggesting its role as a likely mediator of feedback inhibition on the leptin receptor and a potential contributor to physiological leptin resistance (18)

Both the molecules were found to be deeply fit in the active pocket occupying the SH2 domain (46-142 residues). The docking results indicate that both compounds, ALA and SDG, have a strong binding affinity with the target compared to the control drug. It is hypothesized that this binding could prevent the binding of leptin to SOCS3, thereby enabling leptin to bind to its receptor and inhibiting leptin resistance. Upon ligand binding, no changes in conformation were observed, and there were no significant fluctuations, indicating the stability of the

bound complexes. SDG exhibited a greater number of interactions compared to ALA. Based on these results, both SDG and ALA can be considered as potential nutraceuticals for combating obesity.

Conclusion:

Flaxseed has earned attention for its anti-obesity effects. While it has been utilized in traditional medicine for its therapeutic properties, there is a lack of studies investigating the specific mechanisms through which it combats obesity. Therefore, this *in silico* study was conducted to assess the potential activity of two compounds found in flaxseed, SDG and ALA, in regulating obesity via Leptin signalling. The results of this study demonstrate that both SDG and ALA exhibited favourable and stable interactions with the target protein SOCS3. This suggests that these compounds may impede the binding of leptin to SOCS3 by binding to the SH2 domain of the protein. Consequently, these compounds hold promise as potential lead compounds for obesity control. It is important to note that further research is needed to validate these findings and determine the optimal utilization of flaxseed components in combating obesity. By addressing the underlying signalling issues associated with obesity, these compounds could offer a promising approach for future obesity prevention and management strategies.

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Conflict of interest: The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study.

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